

Compounds of Cobalt Chloride with Amines in Non-aqueous Media. Part I

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Compounds of cobalt chloride with primary (mono and di) and secondary amines¹ have been prepared in organic solvents; their properties have been studied and structures discussed.

By passing ammonia gas through cobalt chloride solution, the pentammine is formed in ethanol¹ medium and the diammine in acetone² and methyl acetate³ media. Ephraim⁴ found that four moles of NH_3 combined with CoC_2O_4 , showing the compound to be an unsaturated co-ordinate complex. By the interaction of CoCl_2 and hydrazine hydrochloride in ethanol medium, Ferratini⁵ obtained $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{N}_2\text{H}_4$. Hieber and Ries⁶ prepared the compound $2\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ and reported that the complex obtained with *p*- $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ was more stable than that with the *ortho* derivative.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of the compounds of CoCl_2 with amines in non-aqueous media.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of Merck's or B. D. H. 'extra pure' quality. Ethanol and ethyl acetate were completely dehydrated and distilled before use. Anhydrous cobaltous chloride was prepared by heating the hydrated CoCl_2 in a current of HCl gas.

The compounds were prepared by the addition of an excess of amine in ethyl acetate to cobaltous chloride in ethanol. The precipitate obtained was filtered and washed with ethyl acetate till the washing did not form any precipitate with CoCl_2 solution. Finally the compounds were dried in a vacuum desiccator and analysed.

Cobalt was estimated as the pyridine complex $\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_4(\text{CNS})_2$ and chlorine as silver chloride by Piria and Schiff's method. In a few compounds nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method and the percentage of organic matter calculated. In the rest, it was found by difference.

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, semicrystalline powder, and fairly stable in the dry atmosphere at the room temperature, but begin to hydrolyse slowly

1. Clark, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 230.
2. Neumann and Vogt, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 4334.
3. Neumann and Rill, *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 3791.
4. *Ber.*, 1909, **42**, 3850.
5. *Gazzetta*, 1912, **42**, 165.
6. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1929, **180**, 105.

TABLE I

Amines.	Colour.	Decomp. temp.	%Cobalt.		%Chlorine.		%Nitrogen.		%Organic matter.		Probable formula.
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	
1. α -Naphthylamine	Dirty green	175°	14.00	14.18	17.40	17.06	6.68	6.73	68.20	68.76	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$ (α)
2. β -Naphthylamine	Green	185°	14.08	14.18	17.00	17.06	..	..	68.92	68.76	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2$ (β)
3. Aniline	Blue	..	16.64	18.66	23.12	22.42	8.81	8.86	58.02	58.92	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$
4. <i>o</i> -Toluidine	Light blue	..	16.98	17.14	20.37	20.63	..	..	62.65	62.23	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$ (<i>o</i>)
5. <i>p</i> -Toluidine	Greenish blue	240°	17.20	17.14	20.53	20.63	7.99	8.14	61.80	62.33	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$ (<i>p</i>)
6. <i>m</i> -Toluidine	Blue	245°	16.84	17.14	20.88	20.63	..	..	62.28	62.23	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$ (<i>m</i>)
7. <i>m</i> -Anisidine	Greenish blue	222°	15.03	15.69	18.99	18.87	7.40	7.47	65.38	65.44	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$ (<i>m</i>)
8. <i>p</i> -Anisidine	Blue	200°	14.99	15.69	18.45	18.97	..	..	65.46	65.44	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$ (<i>p</i>)
9. Benzidine	Grey	170°	16.65	16.77	22.20	22.58	..	..	59.15	58.65	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2$
10. <i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	Violet	200°	24.48	24.78	29.58	29.68	11.40	11.70	45.02	45.55	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ (<i>o</i>)
11. <i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	Green	199°	24.48	24.78	29.72	29.68	..	..	45.80	45.55	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ (<i>m</i>)
12. <i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	Grey	195°	24.52	24.78	29.65	29.68	..	..	45.83	45.55	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ (<i>p</i>)
13. <i>o</i> -Dianisidine	Green	249°	16.63	15.77	18.87	18.97	7.26	7.48	61.81	65.26	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{O}(\text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3$ $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{NH}_2)\text{OCH}_3$
14. <i>o</i> -Toluidine	Green	240°	16.84	17.24	20.61	20.74	..	..	62.55	62.02	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3 \cdot (\text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3$ $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(\text{NH}_2)\text{CH}_3$
15. Phenylhydrazine	Black	..	10.98	17.01	20.66	20.50	..	..	62.36	62.46	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{NH}_2$
16. Ethylamine	Black	160°	15.82	15.83	19.02	19.03	7.56	7.52	65.16	65.06	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$
17. Methylamine	Brown	145°	16.28	16.46	19.78	19.81	7.78	7.87	63.59	63.73	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_3$
18. Di- <i>n</i> -butylamine	Green	190°	14.12	14.10	16.80	16.97	..	..	68.09	68.03	$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{NH}_2$

in contact with moist air or when treated with water or dilute alkalis. These are soluble in anhydrous ethanol, sparingly soluble in benzene, and insoluble in CCl_4 . These dissolve in dilute acids, but decompose when treated with strong acids. When heated to a high temperature, they decompose without melting. Analytical data, colour, and decomposition temperature of the compounds are recorded in Table I.

In all the cases two molecules of a monoamine and one molecule of cobaltous chloride combine, showing thereby an attainment of co-ordination number 4 for cobalt. Compounds obtained with diamines are more stable than those with monoamines, probably due to chelation. They may be represented as $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot (2\text{Am})$ (where Am=monoamine) and $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot (2\text{D})$ (where D=diamine). The E.A.N. of cobalt does not assume inert gas configuration and therefore the compounds are not very stable.

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